

Scope for Introduction of AI in Journalism Curriculum: A Scoping Review

Dr. Raja Bhushanam Singavarapu

ABSTRACT

Since the introduction of ‘ChatGPT’ a Generative AI application by ‘OpenAI’ in 2022, there has been a flurry of activity on the possible roles that AI can play in the field of education and the impact it can cause on human development. As the fourth pillar of a democratic society, Journalism plays an important role in human development and needs media for mass dissemination. Journalism is constantly grappling with fast evolving media technologies including Social Media, 360^o Media, Virtual Reality, etc. and before long AI is upon it. Development of AI in news media is happening along four fronts viz. content generation, data analytics and insights, newsroom automation and audience segmentation. However, the curriculum of Journalism courses in India is lagging far behind in terms of digital technology integration. In such a scenario, it is not known if AI can be introduced into Journalism curriculum. This paper sets out to investigate the scope for introduction of AI in educational settings in general and in the curriculum of Journalism and Mass Communication in particular. Towards this a critical review of international policy research and guidelines for the introduction of AI applications in education; design considerations for developers of AI for educational purposes; pedagogical benefits and challenges of AI in Media Education; requirements of digital competencies for students and teachers of journalism; institutional framework for upholding ethical principles of journalism in the AI era; enhancing trust and preventing algorithmic biases in AI based technologies and other related issues; are needed. The methodology used for this research paper is a scoping review of literature to comprehend the extent of available research on the above aspects. The scoping review revealed that AI-based applications do have the potential for aiding journalism studies especially in content creation and curation, audience engagement, automated video editing, predictive analysis, interactive storytelling, etc. However, competency frameworks will have to be developed for students and teachers of Higher Education before introduction of AI-based courses. Further, educational ecosystems should have mutual trust among corporate that offer the technologies, the experts who evaluate and recommend and the educational institutions that procure and use them. In the final count, human oversight in AI-powered media education tools is imperative. In conclusion it can be said that the potential and challenges of AI in education are still being evaluated and it may take a while in introducing AI in Journalism curriculum.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Media Education, Journalism, Digital competencies, Policy research, Guidelines and Institutional frameworks

INTRODUCTION

Newsrooms across the world, including India have already been digitalized and all the fields of AI have found applications for journalism and news media; for purposes of content generation, data analytics and insights, newsroom automation and audience segmentation. These applications are helping journalists to improve their efficiency, checking fake

news and customizing content for target customers, etc; and at the newsroom level to automate back-office tasks, attract subscriptions, etc and at the organization level to cut operating costs. However, issues of algorithmic and other biases in AI applications and upholding ethical principles of journalism while using AI are of serious concern to media practitioners. In

spite of this, it is anticipated that the use of AI by news organizations and journalists is expected to increase at a rapid pace. In such a scenario it is imperative that curriculum for students of journalism is upgraded to include knowledge and use of AI applications. However, it is noticeable that the syllabi of journalism courses are lagging far behind in terms of inclusion of digital technologies.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the international and national policy research recommendations for introduction of AI applications in educational settings and guidelines technology developers?
2. What are the unique and special pedagogical and administrative benefits that can be expected from AI applications in education in general and higher education in particular?
3. What are the competencies that are required by students and teachers to utilize AI?
4. Is there any institutional framework being considered for upholding ethical principles, preventing biases and maintaining trust in journalism in the AI era?
5. What are the available AI-based tools for Journalists, newsrooms and media organizations, and what is the scope for inclusion of training of these in the curriculum at graduation level?

METHODOLOGY

Though it has been in the making since the 1960s, it is only since 2021 that AI has evolved from an emerging technology to real world applications and its applications have boomed since the introduction of Open AI's ChatGPT in 2022. Hence, most of the AI-based applications and their usage are of recent origin and available literature is expected to be limited, particularly in the field of higher education in journalism. To find answers to the research questions that arose for this study, it is presumed that a scoping review of literature may be the most appropriate. The methodology to be followed for this is set out as follows –

- a) Deciding the key words for searching relevant literature on the constructs identified from the research questions and selecting them.
- b) Sorting the most relevant texts for the sub-topics identified for this study.
- c) Charting the data as per the sub-topics, year of publication, type of publication and methodology used.
- d) Analyzing, summarizing, collating the information.

Identifying and sorting relevant literature for the sub-topics

Key word search on the internet, for each of the sub-topics, yielded relevant publications. Sorting was done with the cut-off year as 2019 and selection was done based on type of publication and authenticity. A total of 20 publications were selected for in-depth review and summarization.

Charting the data

The distribution of the selected 20 publications as per their topic of relevance is as follows;

Topic	No of Publications
Policy research recommendations	6
AI in Education and Higher Education	3
AI in Media Education	2
AI Tools for Journalists	4
Training, Curriculum and Syllabus for Courses in AI for Journalism	5
Total	20

The distribution of the selected texts based on the year of publication is as follows;

Year of Publication	No of Publications
2019	2
2020	1
2021	2
2022	-
2023	4
2024	11
Total	20

The distribution of the selected texts based on the type of publication is as follows;

Type of Publication	No. of Texts
Book	3
Journal Articles	4
Conference Papers	1
Website Published Papers	10
Periodical	1
Government Document	1
Total	20

SUMMARY OF THE REVIEWED TEXTS

The information in the selected texts for review is summarized as per the 5 selected topics of relevance.

1. Policy Research Recommendations

i) Beijing Consensus on Artificial Intelligence and Education (2019)

This is an outcome document of the International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Education, with the theme, 'Planning education in the AI era: Lead the leap', held in Beijing, People's Republic of China, 16-18 May, 2019, organized by UNESCO. Around 500 representatives from more than 100 member States, UN agencies, academic institutions, civil society and private sector deliberated on the challenges faced by education and training systems. They recommended that governments and other stakeholders in UNESCO's Member States implement the following actions –

- a) Planning AI in education policies – Align AI in education with public policies on education, take a multi-stakeholder approach to planning and governance of AI in education.
- b) AI for education management and delivery – Develop and integrate AI technologies for upgrading Education management Information Systems (EMIS).
- c) AI to empower teaching and teachers – Develop appropriate capacity-building programmes to prepare teachers to work effectively in AI-based educational settings.
- d) AI for learning and learning assessment – Apply AI tools in a way that the benefits outweigh the risks and facilitate well defined learning tasks in all subjects and develop AI tools for interdisciplinary skills.
- e) Development of values and skills for life and work in the AI era – Develop mechanisms and tools to identify current and future AI literacy skills required for effective human-machine collaboration.
- f) AI for offering lifelong opportunities for all – The guiding principle to be achieving SDG 4, without forgetting the needs of older people, especially older women for living with AI.
- g) Promoting equitable and inclusive use of AI in education – Ensure AI tools for students with learning impairments or disabilities and learning in languages other than mother tongue.
- h) Ensuring ethical, transparent and auditable use of education data and algorithms – Test and adopt tools for ensuring data privacy and security of teachers and learners. Develop regulatory framework to ensure responsible development and use of AI tools for education and learning.
- i) Monitoring, evaluation and research – Develop monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to measure impact of AI on education, teaching and learning.

The delegates of the conference also made recommendations to UNESCO, to establish an 'AI for

Education' platform to act as a clearing house for open-source AI courses and support capacity-building of education policy-makers and expand cooperation with international funding agencies.

ii) AI and Education - Guidance for policy-makers – UNESCO (2021)

UNESCO is entrusted to lead and coordinate the 'Education 2030 Agenda' as per SDG-4 and also as per the 'Beijing consensus 2019'. UNESCO proposes for policy makers 4 categories of AI applications for education –

- (a) Education management and delivery – Educational Chatbots like Ada and Deakin Genie are already providing cloud-based services that answer students' questions. 'Swift' developed by Swift e-learning Services in India, helps EMIS systems in an e-learning mode.
- (b) Learning and assessment – Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) provide individualized tutorials for students. Examples of such learning management systems are Moodle, Open edX and platforms such as Khan Academy. There are 60 commercial ITS available at present including Alef, ALEKS, Byjus, Mathia, etc.
- (c) Empowering teachers and enhancing teaching – There are AI-driven Discussion forums such as AI assistant 'Jill Watson' based on IBM's Watson platform, AI-Human dual teacher platforms such as 'LeWaijiao AI classroom', designed to support human teachers to conduct all of the key tasks, and there are also AI-powered Teaching Assistants.
- (d) Lifelong learning – Currently, there are no commercial AI-enabled lifelong learning products, but research is ongoing.

iii) Education in the age of Artificial Intelligence – UNESCO 2023

All the earlier technologies till date, including digital technologies, online tutorials or Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have never challenged the basic principle of a teacher conducting a class to a group of students. But, the arrival of Generative AI applications such as ChatGPT, are posing unprecedented challenges to the education system. Though AI-based educational applications have immense use for teachers and students, there are issues of the digital divide, data confidentiality, domination of global corporations, etc and at the present time safeguards are not available.

Some of the policy recommendations for regulating AI in educational settings are – A minimum age limit of 13

for use of AI in the classroom, adoption of data protection and privacy standards and organization of specific teacher training. Governments need to regulate use of Generative AI systems in educational institutions, for which the key steps have been outlined in this document. UNESCO warns nations that schools and universities are using AI-based educational tools without any institutional policies or formal guidance and this is mainly due to absence of national guidelines and regulations.

Finally this report recommends that, 'technology should be introduced into education on the basis of evidence showing that it would be appropriate, equitable, scalable and sustainable.

iv) Designing for Education with Artificial Intelligence: An Essential guide for Developers (2024), U.S. Department of Education

The U.S. Department of Education exhorts the developers of AI for educational applications to pay attention to 5 topics of importance for their work –

- (a) Designing for Education – Understand historical discrepancies in opportunities to learn and contribute to equity. Elicit feedback from the educational community throughout the product life cycle and refine the product.
- (b) Provide Evidence for Rationale as well as Impacts – Discuss with potential users relevant local, state or other requirements, form partnerships with researchers.
- (c) Advancing Equity and Protecting Civil Rights – Developers' organizational culture should prioritize data sets used for training algorithms conform to equity and civil rights.
- (d) Ensuring Safety and Security – Draft clear disclosures on student data security and privacy, ensure accountability through audits and testing processes.
- (e) Promoting Transparency and Earning Trust – Demonstrate a commitment to transparency, responsibility and innovation.

v) AI competency framework for students – UNESCO 2024

Only 15 countries in the world have included AI learning objectives in their national student curricula by 2022 and India is not one of them. The key principles for developing AI competency framework for students are – a) Fostering a critical approach to AI, b) Prioritizing human-centered interaction with AI, c) Encouraging environmentally sustainable AI, d) Promoting inclusivity in AI competency development, and e) Building core AI competencies for lifelong

learning. The structure of the framework should be such that it progresses along 3 levels – Understand, Apply and Create. For preparing students to be responsible and creative students in the AI era, 12 competencies have been identified and these align with 4 aspects viz. – Human-centered mindset, Ethics of AI, AI techniques and applications and SI system design.

vi) AI competency framework for teachers – UNESCO 2024

Only 7 countries in the world have developed AI programmes for teachers. UNESCO has developed this competency framework for teachers along with the students' framework. This document lays down the key principles for developing a competency framework for teachers, details the various aspects that are needed for the framework structure and progression levels to be used. The implementation strategies for this framework have been listed as – (i) Regulate AI and ensure trustworthy AI tools for education, (ii) Build enabling policies and conditions for the use of AI in education, (iii) Formulate and adopt local AI competency frameworks for teachers, (iv) Design and streamline training and support programmes on AI competencies, and (v) Develop contextual performance-based assessment tools.

UNESCO exhorts member countries to develop their own national AI competency framework for teachers at the earliest and make arrangements for teacher training programmes. Such programmes have to be based on the principles of inclusivity, centrality of human agency, non-discrimination, and respect for linguistic and cultural diversity.

2.AI in Education and Higher Education

i) Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V.I., Bond, M. *et al.* (2019) - Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education – where are the educators?

The authors conducted a systematic review of all literature available on AI applications in higher educational institutions around the world and identified 2,656 publications of which they selected 146 articles after inclusion and exclusion criteria they used. They found that most of the research conducted was from the disciplines of Computer Science, Science and Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. They also found that the AI in Education was mostly in academic support services and institutional and administrative services, in four areas viz. – Profiling and prediction, Assessment and evaluation, Adaptive systems and personalization and Intelligent tutoring systems. Their review revealed that there is no

pedagogical perspective in the research papers and no critical reflection on the challenges and risks involved in using AI-based applications in higher education.

ii) Kandula, N. (2020) - Role of Artificial Intelligence in Education

The author who is an Assistant Professor in the Department of Artificial Intelligence in an Institute of Technology, reviewed how AI is currently being used in education and found that, AI can automate basic activities in education such as grading, students can get support from AI tutors, AI-driven programmes can give students and teachers feedback, can change the role of the teacher and data powered by AI can change the teaching and learning.

iii) Truong, Y. (2024) AI is an Exciting Opportunity, Not a threat

Writing for AACSB International, a global NGO connecting educators, students and business, Truong, Y., a Professor of Innovation Management, wanted to highlight the inherent limitations of AI, so that students can maximize the benefits that AI tools can provide. He starts by informing that AI is not as intelligent as we may imagine and that AI replacing humans may not be possible at all. Humans work in a web of social relations and they cannot be replaced by machines because their expertise is developed through relations with other humans. Even though AI can outperform doctors in diagnostics and prescriptions, patients will still want to meet a doctor, as humans prefer human interaction. Humans have unique adaptive capabilities and hence will always outperform machines. Hence, students and educators should view the rise of AI as a privileged opportunity to develop new skills and discover new ways to learn and spend time on more rewarding activities.

3. AI in Media Education

i) Samigova, G. A. (2023) - The Importance of Artificial Intelligence in Modern Media Education Technologies in Institutions of Higher Education.

The author, an Associate Professor in Uzbekistan State Institute of Arts and Culture, analyzed the impact of AI and graphics software on media education. For media students courses are available on video content development, audio production, graphic design and virtual reality. Adobe has incorporated AI into numerous apps to enhance and creativity. AI technology in Photoshop offers students and professional enhanced user utility with greater precision, speed and quality. Adobe Premiere Pro uses AI to offer a wide range of tools with enhanced features

for video editing workflow and creation of video content. Canva, a web-based platform uses AI to offer users pre-designed templates for designs that can be customized. AI used in CorelDRAW can automatically align and distribute items on a canvas. The advantages of AI use in graphics programmes are - Automation, Personalized learning, Velocity and efficacy, Analytics and Prediction, and Guidance and assistance; which are particularly useful in media education and design, as they offer interactivity, engagement and help in implementation of ideas.

ii) Sangwan, A. (2024) - Exploring the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Media Education: A Study

The author, an Associate Professor in Journalism and Mass communication, explored the potential implications of AI on media education by analyzing how AI is reshaping media education practices. He conducted a survey of 100 university teachers of media studies, with the objective of analyzing the potential applications of AI in media education, including content creation, curation, and consumption, exploring the implications of AI integration for pedagogy and teaching practices in media education, assessing the impact of AI on student learning outcomes and media literacy skills development, challenges and ethical considerations associated with the integration of AI in media education, and future directions and opportunities for research and practice in the field of AI in media education.

His findings reveal that AI-enabled tools such as automated video editing software, chat bots for interactive storytelling, and predictive analytics platforms provide exciting opportunities for students. He finds that university teachers do acknowledge AI potential for teaching and learning, but technical problems do exist for inclusion in syllabi. Training teachers of media education the necessary skills is immediately required.

4. AI tools for Journalists

i) Mahapatra, P. (2024) AI tools for Journalism

The author, a retired faculty of Journalism, while writing for 'News Writers', informs that London School of Economics conducted a survey of 71 news platforms in 32 countries in 2019 and found that around half of them are using AI for news gathering, two-thirds of them are using it for news product production and half of them are using AI for circulation management. Overall, AI is being used for news gathering from social media posts, investigative reporting and analysis of data collected from multiple sources. The author informs that by the end of 2023, there are around 70 AI

tools available for use in newsrooms. He informs of a tool called 'Klara' which can structure texts, conduct extensive content search and summarize large amount of data quickly and efficiently. 'Bhasini' an AI-based translator being developed by Government of India and Google, will be able to translate English to regional languages with 90% accuracy. AI powered audio transcription applications help in speech-to-text tasks to prepare a text copy of an interview instantly while gathering news for reporting. Voice generating applications such as 'VG's Jojo' help in editing, publishing and sharing audio content; across different platforms. Lead generating tools help in providing advance notice of trends, developing stories for breaking news. Audience engagement tools help moderating audience interactions and comments.

ii) Reilley, M. (2024) Journalist's Tool Box

The website maintained by Reilley, M. provides a comprehensive list of various AI-driven tools available to journalists that can be used for various needs. Only a few are being mentioned here in each category.

(i) AI-Driven Editing and Workflow Tools – A few examples are – 'Quillbot Paraphraser' helps journalists to rephrase any text while ensuring that content retains the correct vocabulary, tone and style; 'Hemingway App' is a free tool that can grade writing for readability; 'Writing Feedback Pro' is a custom GPT offers tips and advice on content without actually rewriting it.

(ii) AI fact checking tools – A few examples are – 'Bellingcat's Digital Forensics Tools' - an open source verification and investigative tools; 'Craig Silverman's Verification and Digital Investigations Resources'; 'Information Laundromat'; 'Information Tracer' - to detect coordinated misinformation campaigns. In fact there are a large number of such tools.

(iii) Images and Multimedia verification / Geolocation tools – A few examples are – 'Deepfake-o-Meter' - A free tool to check images, video and audio; 'Resemble AI' - A paid tool that does spectral audio analysis and detects tiny artifacts' 'Pindrop' - Realtime audio deepfake detection tool.

(iv) AI and Plagiarism Detection Tools – A few examples are – 'GPTZero' - Detects ChatGPT, GPT3, GPT4, Bard and other AI models and has various settings for AI and human+AI; 'CopyLeaks' - Free AI detection tool; 'CheckFor' - Identifies AI-generated content.

(v) AI for Educators – AI tools for journalism education – A large number of tools are available. A few examples are – 'Google: Introduction to AI for Journalists'; Pulitzer Centre: 'Journalism AI Grants'; 'News Literacy in Age of AI'.

The 'Journalist's Tool Box' website provides a comprehensive list of tools available for any type of work that journalist, news editors and newsrooms may require.

iii) Langreo, L. (2023) Beyond ChatGPT: the Other AI tools Teachers are Using

ChatGPT was released by OpenAI in 2022. Since then other such applications have been released such as – 'Bard' by Google and 'Bing Chat' by Microsoft. These applications can provide human-like answers to questions. They are free and easy to use. They can help in writing lesson plans, emails and provide feedback on assignments. ChatGPT has been trained on data available up to 2021, whereas Bard and Bing Chat can provide for up to date information. Bing Chat cites where it got its answers, while Bard and ChatGPT do not.

iv) Philip, R. (2024) New AI and Large Language Model Tools for Journalists: What to Know

The author is a senior journalist with Global Investigative Journalism Network, states that smart and careful use of free or affordable AI tools can be of immense help to front end investigative projects and increases data efficiency, subject briefings, code training, cost saving and public document requests. They allow journalists to spend more time on journalism and less time on tech trouble shooting and coding work. However, responses from Large Language Models (LLMs) are often biased and ethics and copyright problems are issues to be dealt with. He quotes JonKeegan, an investigative data reporter at 'The Markup' who states that reporters and editors need to be systematic in their approach to AI to benefit from its efficiencies. The basic steps recommended by him are – a) Learn how LLMs learn and operate, b) Adopt and communicate a newsroom AI use policy, c) Cut through the confusion about many new AI tools released each week by checking with technical expert sources, d) Be mindful that generative AI tools can take work away from real people, e) Use AI tools at the front end of investigation, rather than at the publication stage and verify everything they produce. He informs the AI tools recommended by 2024 NICAR Data Journalism Conference panelists, which are – Rolli Information Tracer and Rolliapp, GPT Excel, GitHub CoPilot, ChatGPT or Claude, Perplexity, and Llamafile.

5. Training, Curriculum and Syllabus for Courses in AI for Journalism

i) Google News Initiative (2024) - Introduction to AI for Journalists

This document is actually a lesson providing details of Google's approach to AI, the history of AI, details of what Generative AI is all about, Google's AI principles, Google's AI tools for journalists and best practices to be followed. The Google's AI powered tools for journalists are –

Pinpoint – a tool built specifically to meet the needs of journalists to uncover information.

Fact Check Explorer – a tool to fact check reports already investigated and published by independent organizations around the world. Gemini – previously called is a product to help use Generative AI.

ii) London School of Economics (2024) - Training for AI in Journalism

This is a free online course designed by Journalism AI in collaboration with Texty and the support of Google News Initiative and was launched on 7 December, 2020. The course teaches journalists how to use Machine learning for their reporting and how to train a Machine Learning model to identify and classify images in vast datasets. The course has 6 modules which can be explored independently too. The 6 modules are - 1) Machine Learning, journalism and you, 2) Is machine learning the same thing as AI?, 3) Different approaches to machine learning, 4) How you can use machine learning, 5) How does a machine learn?, and 6) bias in machine learning.

iii) Knight Centre for Journalism in the Americas (2024) - Investigative Reporting Now – OSINT and other cutting edge tools and techniques

Knight Center for Journalism in the Americas, at the University of Texas, is professional training and outreach centre for journalists. From 2012 it has been offering distance learning programmes as Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) to journalists around the world. It offers courses on a wide range of subjects for journalists. Some of the AI-based courses on offer are –

- 1) Generative AI for journalists: Discovering what data can do. This is a paid course.
- 2) The impact of AI on elections and freedom of expression. This course is free.

iv) Aboh, B. (2021) - Artificial Intelligence and Algorithms in Journalism

Aboh, B., is an innovative leader with over 14 years experience in Data Analytics, AI and Product Innovation. He is conducting a course for journalists on the Udeemy educational platform on the topic – 'Introduction to AI and News Algorithms'. This is a paid course having 3 sections and 17 lectures.

v) Indian Institute of Mass Media, Department of New Media – PG Diploma in Digital Media, Syllabus 2024-2025

It is only recently that curriculum in Journalism and Mass Communication courses are introducing syllabi on Digital Media. An example is the Department of New Media in Indian Institute of Mass Communication, which has included the subjects that fall under digital media.

Paper-10: Emerging Technologies

Unit 1: Artificial Intelligence, Unit 2: Augmented Reality, Unit 3: Virtual Reality

Paper 8: Fact Checking & Verification

Unit 1: Introduction to Misinformation Ecosystem, Unit 2: Types of Misinformation and Disinformation, Unit 3: Fact Checking Visuals, Unit 4: Fact Checking Location

Paper 6: Content Management System:

Unit 1: Introduction to CMS, Unit 2: Introduction to HTML, Unit 3: Working with WordPress, Joomla and Drupal, Unit 4: Design and Development of Digital Portal

Paper 4: Multimedia Content Creation for Journalism

Unit 1: Introduction to Journalism, Unit 2: Writing for News Media, Unit 3: Multimedia Journalism, Unit 4: Production Techniques and Methods

Paper 2: Understanding Digital Media

Unit 1: Understanding Media Landscape, Unit 2: Understanding Digital Media & its Characteristics, Unit 3: Internet as a Medium & Digital Audiences, Unit 4: Digital Media: Political Economy & International Relations

CONCLUSION

It has been revealed from the scoping review conducted that international policy recommendations for introduction of AI applications in educational settings have been laid out mainly by the UNESCO. AI applications in education in general and higher education in particular have been reviewed and found that the present uses are mainly for educational delivery, teaching aids, assessment and evaluation, and such other functions; but the actual pedagogical benefits to the students are yet to be fully evaluated. The competencies required for students and teachers to utilize AI applications effectively have been discussed in the policy section and these have to be taken up at the governmental and institutional levels. The necessity for having institutional framework for upholding ethical principles, preventing biases and maintaining trust have been discussed in the policy

section and every news media organization has to have its own policy which has to properly disseminated among all its departments. AI-based tools are available for all needs of journalists, newsrooms and media organizations, which have been discussed in the 'AI-tools for journalists' section. Before the curriculum for journalism students can be introduced with subjects dealing with AI, the competencies of teachers needs to be upgraded and institutional facilities have to be upgraded and only then can the competencies of the students be developed. A few universities and colleges have started to introduce digital media and AI courses in their curriculum and the Department of new Media, at the Indian Institute of Mass Media is an example. However, it has done it at the post-graduate level, which has to be started at the graduate level. In conclusion it can be said that the potential and challenges of AI in education are still being evaluated and it may take a while in introducing AI in Journalism curriculum.

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